

Studies in the Protective Action of Colloids. Part III. Influence of Sucrose and Sodium Oleate on the Stability of Colloid Manganese Dioxide.

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It was observed previously (Joshi and Lal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 63) that presence of sucrose did not affect sensibly the kinetics of coagulation of the above sol by potassium and barium chloride. Further work showed that this sol was coagulated under certain conditions, by the addition of sucrose, which is interesting. While a number of electrolytes are known to *sensitise*, that is, to increase the coagulative power of the electrolyte added, coagulation and the concomitant change of properties initiated by substances like sugar alone appear to have been hitherto examined not in detail. The present paper records work carried out with sucrose and sodium oleate from the view point just mentioned.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sol was prepared, and its colloid content estimated as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). The last quantity before mixing with the solutions of the protector was 0.75 g. of MnO_2 per litre in all the experiments. The sol having been prepared by Cuy's method (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 415) contained traces of KOH. In view of the fact that viscosity reveals perhaps to the greatest extent but small changes produced in a colloid, the above action of the protector added in different proportions was studied by measuring variations in this property. The experimental arrangement of measuring viscosity was that due to Scarpa (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271; *cf.* also Farrow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347) with modifications described in a previous paper (this number, Joshi and Viswanath, p. 329). The temperature of the thermostat in all the experiments was 35°. The solutions of sucrose and sodium oleate used were made from Merck's guaranteed pure materials. Viscosity was measured 15 minutes after mixing the colloid with any of the protecting solutions. Measurement of viscosity was repeated at least twice and the results

agreed within 0.1% in each case. This observation was taken soon after mixing, since after long periods of time, coagulation occurred in some of the solutions and then the corresponding value of viscosity was less reproducible than above. The viscometer used in experiments with sodium oleate (Tables III, IV) was different from that used with sucrose solutions (Tables I, II).

TABLE I.

Protector used = 50% sucrose.

No.	Composition of the mixture			t_1 .	t_2 .	Viscosity.	Remarks.
	Sol.	Sugar.	Water.				
1	16 c. c.	4 c. c.	...	7' 35"	5' 20"	1.181	The sol coagulated appreciably after 24 hrs. The corresponding value was 1.21
2	..	3	1 c. c.	6' 47"	5' 3"	1.123	
3	..	2	2	6' 34"	4' 51"	1.082	
4	..	1	3	7' 26"	4' 59"	1.178	

TABLE II.

Protector used = 25% sucrose.

1	..	4	...	7' 15"	5' 2"	1.18	Slight coagulation observed after 24 hrs.
2	..	3	1	5' 50"	4' 47"	1.018	
3	..	2	2	5' 25"	4' 10"	0.915	
4	..	1	3	6' 20"	4' 52"	1.07	

TABLE III.

Protector used = 0.334% sodium oleate.

	Sol.	Sodium oleate.	Water.	t_1 .	t_2 .	Viscosity.	
1	10 c. c.	10 c. c.	...	1' 35"	2' 21.4"	0.757	Coagulates after about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr.
2	..	8	2	1' 33"	2' 20"	0.744	Coagulates after about 1 hr.
3	..	6	4	1' 32.4"	2' 19"	0.741	Coagulation observed to be appreciable after only 24 hrs.
4	..	5	5	1' 32.2"	2' 20"	0.742	
5	..	4	6	1' 34"	2' 18"	0.745	
	..	3	7	1' 31.6"	2' 18.5"	0.749	
7	..	2	8	1' 35"	2' 19"	0.752	

TABLE IV.

Protector used = 0.167% sodium oleate.

No.	Sol.	Sodium oleate.	Water.	t_1 .	t_2 .	Viscosity.	Remarks.
1	10 c. c.	10 c. c.	...	1' 10"	2' 5.9"	0.599	Coagulates in about 2 hrs.
2	„	8	2 c. c.	1' 8"	2' 4"	0.585	Coagulates after about 24 hrs.
3	„	6	4	1' 7"	2' 3.1"	0.578	
4	„	5	5	1' 6.8"	2' 4.4"	0.58	
5	„	4	6	1' 7.5"	2' 4.8"	0.58	
6	„	3	7	1' 7.7"	2' 5"	0.585	
7	„	2	8	1' 8.1"	2' 5.1"	0.587	

DISCUSSION.

For its well known capillary activity, its high 'gold number', and such allied properties as its detergent and peptising action, sodium oleate is regarded, in general, as a typical protecting agent. The coagulation of the sol on its admixture is, therefore, interesting, and particularly the fact that this effect is greater at larger proportions of sodium oleate. With lower amounts of the latter, the sol remained unchanged for at least 48 hours. These results suggest an interrelation, perhaps a possible merging of a protector with a coagulator under change of conditions, here simply by increasing the concentration of the oleate added. In this connection it is interesting to point out that faintly acid Donau gold sol, or a Carey Lea silver sol is coagulated upon the addition of but small amounts of gelatine, the last being freed of electrolytes as much as possible (Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," Eng. Trans., 1926, pp. 582-583). This has been ascribed by Freundlich and Löning (*loc. cit.*, p. 585) to the presence of oppositely charged colloid ions present in such hydrophiles. With the exception of our observation that the coagulating effect diminishes by reducing the concentration of sodium oleate added, the above explanation would appear in the main to be applicable to our results, since the existence of colloid ions in soap solutions is now well recognised.

The last factor is absent in sucrose solutions, and coagulations due to them (Tables I, II) cannot, therefore, be explained on the above

view. This type of change would appear to be classifiable with the so-called sensitisation, produced in general by soluble non-electrolytes. The pioneer work in this field is by Kruyt and van Duin (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1914, 5, 269), Wo. Ostwald, who was the first to emphasise the variability of the dielectric constant in such cases (*cf.* Freundlich and Rona, *Biochem. Z.*, 1917, 81, 87), Cussuto (*cf.* Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 1253) and especially Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," p. 463). Freundlich proceeds on the simple assumption of an analogy of a colloid particle enclosed in the 'Helmholtz double layer', with a charged condenser. Since non-electrolytes usually possess comparatively low dielectric constants, their adsorption would lead to a diminution of the last quantity. A reduction in the charge, the stability of the colloid particle and therefore, in the adsorption of the opposite ions required for coagulation, is to be anticipated as a necessary consequence. The insufficiency of this view is shown by the work of Rona and György (*Biochem. Z.*, 1920, 105, 133), Weiser (*loc. cit.*), Sen (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 310) and Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Roy Choudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 493, *et seq.*). It is seen that changes in dielectric constant alone can not be considered as the sole determinant of sensitisation. Furthermore, it is tacitly assumed in Freundlich's theory that sensitisation is necessarily preceded by the adsorption of the non-electrolyte on the colloid by virtue of its capillary activity.

The difficulty of applying the last postulate to our results with sugar is evident from the observation of Bhatnagar, Srivastav and Gupta (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, 37, 101) that the adsorption of sugar on MnO_2 is but insensible. It would also appear from a survey of the literature that a marked capillary activity is not necessarily the characteristic of a sensitiser. Moreover, this action is a specific one both as to the nature of the non-electrolyte and the coagulator. Thus for example, Sen (*loc. cit.*) has observed, in the coagulation of the MnO_2 sol by copper sulphate and silver nitrate in the presence of ethyl alcohol and sucrose, that the former stabilises the sol against copper sulphate more than silver nitrate. Also, using the last electrolyte, sucrose did not exert any appreciable effect, as we found previously in coagulations by potassium and barium chloride (Joshi and Lal, *loc. cit.*). A further important element in Freundlich's theory is that sensitisers do not initiate coagulation but merely augment it due to added electrolytes (Freundlich and Rona, *loc. cit.*; Rona and György, *loc. cit.*).

The observation of Freundlich that no alteration is produced even after long time when the arsenious sulphide sol is mixed with a number of non-electrolytes added in large concentrations (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **44**, 136) is at variance with that of Klein (*Kolloid Z.*, 1921, **29**, 247) who observed coagulation in the above and other colloids by the addition of non-electrolytes, in the absence of any added electrolytes. Similarly Billitzer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **45**, 312) using a platinum sol and Wo. Ostwald (*cf.* Weiser, *loc. cit.*) using a silver sol observed that they can be coagulated by adding suitable amounts of alcohols. Recently Patel and Desai (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, **51**, 318) observed that a *long-dialysed* thorium hydroxide sol can also be coagulated by non-electrolytes alone. In the main, these results would appear to be in line with ours (Tables I, II), and are to be ascribed to the appreciable alteration of the nature of the dispersion medium.

It is very interesting to note the initial fall of viscosity at low proportions of the sodium oleate and sugar added. A strikingly similar diminution of viscosity has been noted by a number of workers when a given volume of colloid is treated with successively small increments of *electrolytes* (Gokun, *Z. Chem. Ind. Kolloid*, 1908, **3**, 84; Woudstra, *ibid.*, 1911, **8**, 73; Farrow, *loc. cit.*; Dhar and Chakravarti, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1646). In view of the lack of a definite knowledge of the factors which determine completely the viscosity of a colloid, it is not surprising to note the diverse, and at places conflicting explanations of the above phenomenon by different workers; more experimental work is needed to elucidate it. Meanwhile it is interesting to note the occurrence of the same effect in the presence of a non-electrolyte and a typical protecting agent like sodium oleate.

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Received May 15, 1933.

